

**“De-Stereotyping Body and Desires”: A Study A. Revathi's
*The Truth about Me***

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Abstract

Ever since the narratives of human existence have been recorded, every creature is supposed to have belonged to a particular gender. This heteronormative gender colonization has resulted in the suppression of the voices of gay men, lesbians, bisexuals, transgender and other such populace. A. Revathi, while disclosing the maze of the lives of one such category i.e. transgender in her autobiography, The Truth about Me, has valiantly tried to establish her identity in heteronormative society which has its own specific dimensions. Defying the norms and expressing her utter disgust towards masculine body and her desire for female genitals, A. Revathi is the first transgender in India to write an autobiography. This study through multiple layered discussions of Revathi's autobiography in the light of queer theory encapsulates her journey towards “de-stereotyping body and desires” (Rao 12) and configures the effect of the constructed male and female categories on transgender people.

Keywords: Heteronormative society, transgender, queer, body, desires, gender

To perpetuate its hegemonic gender discourse of male/female, heteronormative society employs every tact. The purpose of this paper is to study the effect of this constructed binary opposition i.e. male/female and the performative nature of monolithic gender categories on transgender through an understanding of A. Revathi's *The Truth about Me*, originally written in Tamil and translated in English by V. Geetha. Born with a male body, having feminine sensibilities, Revathi challenged the culturally legitimate definition of gender itself. Almost untouched by the critics, the autobiography punctures the teleological narratives which have compartmentalized the people into specific gender identities. The study will also unravel the bizarre economical, social, ethical, moral, and cultural practices which have pushed the transgender people to the fringes of the main stream society. They are ridiculed, hooted, rejected and jeered and were not even having equal rights before April 15, 2014 in India. Commonly known as *hijras* which refers to “a transgendered person, a physiological male who adopts a feminine gender identity, women's clothing and other feminine gender roles” (Samanta 220), they are marginalized in socio-political context in India. A. Revathi while raising her voice against all such social practices and cultural politics of gender introduced the “third sex”.

Queer theory as propounded by Michel Foucault, Judith Butler and Adrienne Rich mainly appears to be a Western import. The Indian critics like Brinda Bose,

Pramod Nayar, Niladri Chatterjee and so on have interpreted it, yet there is a need to develop an indigenous queer theory. R. Raj Rao, an Indian gay-rights activist and critic represented this queerness through the phrase “de-stereotyping body and desire” (Rao 12) which is quite similar to Oscar Wilde's anti-essentialism, to Derrida's idea of deconstructing the binaries, and to Foucault's destabilizing normativity. The transgender people live with an ambivalence between their biological body and psychological desires as is observed in the case of A. Revathi. The socially approved categories of gender assume and expect different language, dressing sense, behavior, attitude, culture and so on from both the gender which is just “a performative gesture” as formulated by Butler. This “compulsory heterosexualization of desire” as said by Adrienne Rich (Sedgwick 36) is responsible for the ghettoized lives of other gender categories.

The word “hijra” is derived from Semitic Arabic root 'hjr' meaning “leaving one's tribe”. Usually, a transgender is an effeminate man, inclined to attain the identity of a woman and thereby leaving his status quo given at birth. Baptized as Doraisamy by her parents, Revathi “was born last in a family of five brothers and three sisters” (Revathi 2). Now the question is how to refer to the child Doraisamy – he/she – in the binary system of language, constructed for and by the heteronormative society. There is no pronoun which can be used for the third gender which shows that these people have only epistemological existence without having any ontological existence. For this particular paper, the pronoun “he” has been used for the child Doraisamy and “she” for the grown up Revathi. Doraisamy grew up imagining himself to be a girl:

I think I must have been around ten, studying in class 5. I would go to the village school along with the girls from the neighbourhood and return with them. I played only girls' games. I loved to sweep the frontyard clean and draw the *kolam* every morning. (Revathi 3)

From his childhood he felt uneasiness while negotiating his body's incongruity with his inner desires. The family structure did not allow him to grow up with such body and desires and for his every flaw physical punishment used to be the answer. He was scolded, beaten, and warned time and again to mend his ways and to behave like a boy. Even the teacher in his school punished and reprimanded him for his feminine behavior:

I remember being canned for 'not being brave like a boy' . . . I didn't know that I behaved like a girl; it felt natural for me to do so . . . It was like eating for me – just as I would not stop eating because someone asked me not to eat. I felt I could not stop being a girl, because others told me not to be so. (Revathi 7)

This strange desire to be a woman within the male body always left him perplexed and he used to question himself “Would the world accept me thus?” because he longed to be with women but used to feel ashamed by that feeling. The desire to look like woman within him is to realize the true self.

As a child, once he got a chance to play the role of Chandramathi in the play Harishchandra, and in that role of a woman, he felt like enlivening himself, “to the world, it appeared that I was dressing up and playing a woman, but inside, I

felt I was a woman. (Revathi 12)

The dress is a significant marker of heteronormative gender code; 'cross-dressing' is regarded as primary step towards fulfilling one's desires. Revathi in her autobiography narrates multiple instances where she dressed like a girl. Doraisamy let his hair grow, used to "twist a long towel" around his head and "let it trail down" at his back "like a braid" (Revathi 4). The gender specific dressing pattern through its binary norms again creates a hegemonic discourse. The lives of "others" oscillate between two dressing patterns. The heteronormative society perpetuates "two contingent boxes of genders, male and female, considers those hanging outside the boxes as outcasts" (Boxi 298). On many occasions, he used to dress up like girls and when later on somebody pointed out that he looked like the actress Revathi, he immediately became conscious of his femininity. He imagined that his name was Revathi. He looked at himself in the mirror and felt a glow of pride. He felt like a woman. It was at that moment that he was convinced he was indeed a woman.

Even when he joined the *hijra* community, he found this dress code playing power politics there also, as only the sari-clad people were given respect. This shows that the transgender people also try to fit into the constructed homogeneous gender categories and are quite unaware of the idea of fluid or heterogeneous gender identity which the queer theorists propounded. Doraisamy's anxiety and desire to lead a life of woman made him leave his native place and join a group of people like him which soon made him realize the difficulties of being a transgender. The *Guru* christened Doraisamy as 'Revathi', accepted her as her daughter and as a woman. When Doraisamy as a woman came back home, he was harassed and beaten up mercilessly for bringing shame to the family. Doraisamy, now Revathi, prays to the shrine:

"Amma! Why I must suffer like this . . . I have known only pain . . . It was you who made me in form, but with female feelings. And now, for your crime, I am being punished in your own shrine. . . . Can't you understand another woman's feelings?" (Revathi 57)

Transgender, gay, lesbian, bi-sexual individuals have existed in every race, culture, class, nation, caste etc. In the so called "civil societies" in India, the transgender people are not only denied employment, accommodation, public toilets but also harassed, exploited and murdered. A biological disorder i.e. a bungling up of X and Y chromosomes in the human body make them a menace, a nuisance or even extra-terrestrials in the eyes of an average Indian. A. Revathi was even not allowed to take a husband or steady man. "Why did I love men? Was I the only one who felt this way? Or were there others like me . . . if indeed they were there?" (Revathi 14). Under her *Guru*, after leaving her family, she had only three options, either to beg, or bless or indulge in sex work:

. . . men and even women stared at us and laughed, and heckled us. I realized what a burden a *hijra's* daily life is. Do people harass those who are men and women when they go out with their families? Why a crippled person, a blind person - even they attract pity and people help them . . . but we - we are not considered human. (Revathi 83)

Each step she took for de-stereotyping her body and desires – from leaving her family to nirvana or castration – she felt constrained and controlled by the rules and demands of the society. She moved from city to city in her desire to live freely and to be a woman.

She fights against all odds, stands against all obstacles, voices against all unfair only to stay true to her feeling by breaking all social and cultural politics of the concept of gender and introducing the third sex. (Das 086)

Commonly known as *hijra*, *Chhakka*, *Bambaiya*, *khusra*, *kojja* and *Aravani*, these transgender people are ghettoized in India. Their hoarse and appalling voices at railway stations, bus stands and market places reveal their wretched life while creating an unknown terror simultaneously. They are forced and thwarted to live their lives by singing “badhai” songs on ceremonies. The “. . . biological dissimilarities push them towards an unkind zone of the society where in they are betrayed and forced to lead a treacherous life” (Gowda 23). Revathi was not given right on the ancestral property and when she showed her inclination towards a man, she was chided.

As a result the transgender opt for nirvana, a process through which they try to liberate themselves from entrapped gender identity, and eventually find themselves in another trap. They are ostracized and as a result remain illiterate so they lack even what Gramsci calls “conscious leadership” or “the restless impulse or instant to revolt”. In case of Revathi, this nirvana operation added to another misery. It was not like dressing up as a woman to fulfill one's desires, rather a life-threatening operation which was carried out in unhygienic conditions also: “I lay writhing in pain for nearly two hours and then felt a huge pressure on my chest . . . bile rushed up to my throat . . . at that time it seemed as if I would surely die” (75).

After the nirvana operation, when Revathi decided to be a sex worker, she was harassed and assaulted by the clients as well as the police. She was even stripped by a rowdy and saved herself by running to the nearest building. The ordeals and torments she experienced because of her body and desires are heart-rending. Her choice of taking up sex work which she initially took up in order to fulfill her sexual desires later on proved havoc for her as belonging to the category of sexual minority in itself resulted in torture. The brutality was inflicted in the form of the assaults, the rapes and the violence committed on her body not only by male clients but also by the policemen.

I fell at the policeman's feet. He kicked me with his boots. He then asked me to take my clothes off – right there, while the prisoner was watching. I pleaded with him and wept . . . when I was standing naked, he struck his *lathi* where I had had my operation . . . struck at that part with his *lathi* . . . there was not a soul there to take pity on me. (Revathi 206)

In the same autobiography while narrating her own trauma, Revathi expresses the concerns of the people like her. She mentions how one of her acquaintances used to hide his feminine feelings, used to keep moustache as a mark of masculinity but used to wear saris secretly. He being the only son in the family couldn't leave his

family. Revathi expresses his helpless condition in relentless words: “. . . hiding his feminine feelings, expressing them only on the hill fort.”

The physical, spiritual and the emotional traumas which Revathi felt because of the oppressive Gurus, her desire to have gender identity in a stereotypical society, her family conflict over the parental property, and many such issues made her to move towards *Sangama* where she raised her voice for the people like her.

Under the acronym LGBT, many organizations in modern India have now come up to unearth the lives and concerns of transgender people, their education, marriages, income, job opportunities and other related issues. However, they fail to challenge the rigid definition of gender. Judith Butler questions the stability of binary sex and suggests a radical discontinuity between sexed bodies and culturally constructed genders.

Assuming for the moment the stability of binary sex, it does not follow that the construction of 'men' will accrue exclusively to the bodies of males or that 'women' will interpret only female bodies. Further, even if the sexes appear to be unproblematically binary in their morphology and constitution (which will become a question), there is no reason to assume that genders ought also to remain as two. (Butler 345)

Revathi is now one such activist who works with *Sangama*, a Bangalore based NGO for sexual minorities facing oppression. “Revathi defied *hijra* custom by taking a paying job at *Sangama*, where she learned about her rights, about what could be done to educate other people about those rights. *Sangama* gave Revathi the language to express her dissatisfaction and her desires, her need for her *hijra* sisters as well as her discomfort within their confining homes. . . ” (Gowda 26). By joining this wider world with new perception and changed attitude, she is doing every possible effort to reclaim the identity of the transgender people in the heteronormative society. Although her whole life is a conflict between her body and her desires, but she finds a true self and a new dimension by fighting for the general acceptance of her community.

The autobiography is a direct, honest, heartfelt and frank expression of her grave thoughts and feelings. The purpose is not to gain sympathy rather to make the heteronormative society aware of the fact that the transgender people are also human beings. While narrating the ruthless practice of the stereotypical society, her fierce and passionate espousal of the rights for dignity, acceptance and respect as a human being, is quite evident throughout the autobiography. In the *Preface* she writes:

In our society we speak the languages of rights loud and clear and often. But do the marginalised have access to their rights? Individuals are denied their rights in the name of sex, sexuality, caste and religion. They have to either arrive at compromise or engage in a struggle. I am one such individual who has been marginalized because I was born a male and wanted to live my life as a woman. *The Truth about Me* is about my everyday experience of discrimination, ridicule and pain; it is also about my endurance and my joys. As a *hijra* I get pushed to the fringes of society. Yet I dared to share my

innermost life with you—about being a *hijra*... my aim is to introduce to the readers the lives of *hijras*, their distinct culture, and their dreams and desires. (Revathi v)

The immeasurable sufferings and agonies of the transgender people because of being abandoned by the heteronormative society are still unknown as even the grand narratives set through literature and cinema only add to the jaundiced view of them by depicting them in the same roles which are assumed for them by the society, the notable exceptions are Pooja Bhatt's film *Tamanna* and Akshya Kumar's film *Laxmii*. There are references to Kinnars, Shikhandi, Brihannala and so on in ancient Indian scriptures but their purpose was to serve the larger community. They have never been found speaking for themselves. Eli Clare, a transgender poet, expresses:

Grappling with this lack of self-writing by or accurate information about these individuals . . . I want to hear the stories, but like the stories of other marginalized people, they were most often never told, but rather eaten up, thrown away, lost in the daily grind of survival. (78)

Transgender people are quite visible both in popular literature and daily life, still they face discrimination, stigma and systematic inequality not only in India but across the world.

Despite a recent U.S. Supreme Court Decision that makes it clear that trans people are legally protected from discrimination in the workplace, there is still no comprehensive federal non-discrimination law that includes gender identity—which means trans people may still lack recourse if they face discrimination when they're seeking housing or dining in a restaurant. ("Understanding")

Along with poverty, transgender people face enormous health disparities, including staggering rates of HIV infection, lack of primary care (including individualized, medically necessary transition-related healthcare), and high rates of attempted suicide. Black transgender women in many countries experience frightening levels of physical violence. This is particularly true among transgender people participating in sex work and other informal or criminalized economies. Brutal murders of transgender women occur with such alarming regularity, often with little response from law enforcement, that the American Medical Association declared violence against transgender people an epidemic in 2019.

Thus, everyday experiences of the transgender people are filled with shame, discrimination and harassment which make them vulnerable to violence, rape and sexual assault. A. Revathi's autobiography *The Truth about Me: A Hijra Life Story* has brought the question of transgender community in literary field and turned the attention of the readers towards their denigrated status. This autobiography, "a travelogue of travails" (Galani 75) is still waiting to be hailed by critics. Having a male body, expected to exhibit masculine traits and behavior, expressing the desire to be a woman and declaring the arrival of third sex, A. Revathi broke the stereotypical categorization of male and female. While establishing her identity through her self-narrative which is not only a grim tale of her experiences but also an expression

against the established traditions, norms and taboos of the society, she de-stereotyped her body and desires. She brings to light the agony, torture, trauma and pain of being forced to live in the fringes of the society.

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